

AGRO4AGRI

FOSTERING THE ADVANCED USE
OF AGROCHEMICALS FOR A
SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE

agro4agri.eu

THE PROJECT

AGRO4AGRI is an EU-funded project that brings together 12 European research centres, leading universities and innovative companies from 7 different countries to revolutionise plant nutrition and protection through cutting-edge nano and biotechnology.

Our main goal is to deliver innovative agrochemical solutions, under the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework, to enhance fertiliser efficiency and develop species-specific nematicides that reduce the use of traditional agrochemicals

THE AGRO4AGRI SOLUTION

Advanced nano and biobased controlled delivery systems for plant fertilisers and biostimulants

Target-specific, sustainable nematicides based on RNA interference (RNAi) technology

Nanocellulose hydrogels for a slow water delivery

Low-risk active substances for operators and the environment, which also allow for a reduction in wash-out

We aim to cut nutrient and pesticide use, promoting sustainable and eco-friendly solutions, in line with the European Green Deal and the Farm to Fork Strategy for a more sustainable and competitive agrifood sector in the EU

WORK PACKAGES

WHAT IS OUR WORKFLOW?

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